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Innovative Climate-Control System to Extend Range of Electric Vehicles and Improve Comfort (XERIC)

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Summary:

This is the first of XERIC’s e-newsletters. The e-newsletters will be released twice a year.

This deliverable explains how the e-newsletters are created and sent and what makes up the mailing lists.

The newsletter is then displayed, along with the coordinator’s full editorial.

Document history and validation

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1. Creating and sending e-newsletters

The e-newsletters are created thanks to *MailPoet* and the *WordPress* Content Management System.

The e-newsletters are sent automatically as emails. The software splits the mailing list and doesn't send the e-newsletter to more than 30 persons at a time so that the e-newsletter is not considered as a spam.

The receivers can either view the e-newsletter directly in the message body or open a page in their browser.

2. Mailing lists

We have created 3 mailing lists for the different communication purposes that we may have.

- List 1 : all the persons working for XERIC at XERIC's partners';
- List 2 : other persons at XERIC's partners' it may be nice to inform about XERIC's existence, activities and big annual workshops;
- List 3 : other persons not part of XERIC whom the partners want to be aware of XERIC.

TOTAL : 123 persons.

XERIC's 1st e-newsletter has been sent to all 3 mailing lists

3. Newsletter 1

See next page.

Newsletter 1 - December 2015

Editorial by Nino Gaeta

XERIC's European adventure has started! Welcome to the XERIC project and to our first newsletter.

We have just concluded the first semester of activities of a very challenging and exciting scientific and technological adventure for the market of electric vehicles... and for ourselves, the people involved in XERIC.

This first newsletter aims at providing you with an introduction to XERIC. It is the first in a series of biannual e-newsletters that will keep you posted on XERIC's progresses.

Range limitation is one of the major drawbacks of electric vehicles... and that's the **main challenge taken up by XERIC: extending the range of electric vehicles by developing a novel climate control system.** (...)

Nino Gaeta - GVS spa - XERIC's Coordinator

[Read more](#)

XERIC in a Nutshell

XERIC is a **European Research and Innovation project**. Its objective is to develop an **energy-friendly climate-control system** capable of **reducing at least 50% the energy used** for passenger comfort throughout the year (i.e., heating, cooling and dehumidifying).

XERIC's climate control system should:

- reduce by more than 50% the energy used for passenger comfort;
- have a lifetime superior to 10 years;
- enable easy industrialisation and customisation for electric vehicles currently on the market;
- cost between 1200 and 3000 € per vehicle.

[Read more](#)

XERIC's Partners

First-class research groups are working hand in hand with innovative industrial companies to reach XERIC's challenging objectives.

The University of Genova is also part of the project, as third party.

[Read more](#)

XERIC's Website

Our website has gone public a few weeks ago!

Don't hesitate to visit it to discover why XERIC is transdisciplinary and to get into the details of XERIC's scientific and technological challenges:

www.xeric.eu

XERIC's Brochure

Download XERIC's brochure to learn all about XERIC at a single glance:

[Xeric's brochure](#)

More on the following page. →

Automotive and R&D Networks in Bologna's region

XERIC's partners received as a special guest Dr. Gabriella Gualandi, from ASTER, during XERIC's kick-off meeting in June 2015 in Bologna, Italy.

ASTER is the Emilia-Romagna High-Tech Network, dedicated to promoting technological innovation in industry. Dr. Gualandi gave a very informative talk on "Automotive and R&D networks in Emilia Romagna: Opportunities for XERIC". We'll be sure to make the most of it.

On to Clustering!

Clustering with other EC-funded projects is a must for XERIC: a **first clustering meeting** was organised in November in Kaiserslautern, Germany, with representatives from the JOSPEL and OPTEMUS projects: **cross-fertilisation** is very much on the agenda, as you'll see by reading the next entry of this newsletter.

More on the following page. →

One-day Event for Electric Mobility in Bologna

Save the date! XERIC will be organising a one-day event devoted to **electric mobility** in November 2016 in Bologna, Italy.

The more, the merrier: the JOSPEL and OPTEMUS projects said yes to contributing to the event. Information about programme, venue and registration will be regularly posted on XERIC's website.

ASTER, Emilia-Romagna's High-Tech Network, will provide its know-how to make a success of this event.

The **full Editorial** by XERIC's coordinator is displayed on the following page.

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Range limitation is one of the major drawbacks of electric vehicles... and that's the main challenge taken up by XERIC: **extending the range of electric vehicles by developing a novel climate control system**. We are developing a hybrid-system based upon an **innovative three-fluids-combined membrane contactor (3F-CMC)** that simultaneously works with air, desiccant solution and refrigerant. It could **renew consumer interest** in electric vehicles and plug-in hybrid cars and thus **boost the growth of the electric vehicles market in Europe**.

I am particularly confident in XERIC's consortium and its **transdisciplinary approach**: all partners contribute their unique expertise and also work outside their discipline to understand and contribute to the project's objective. The **resulting synergy** is a thrilling approach.

We're also looking for synergy by **clustering with other EC-funded projects**: a first clustering meeting was organised in November in Kaiserslautern, Germany, with representatives from the JOSPEL and OPTEMUS projects: cross-fertilisation is very much on the agenda! We look forward to joining resources with these two projects to implement combined dissemination actions and expand the reciprocal knowledge.

Also on behalf of the partners, I am glad to report that we are strongly committed to make XERIC a **successful journey creating new intellectual and material know-how** leading to the reduction of energy consumption for heating, ventilation and air conditioning in electric cars, and in general in air-conditioned environments.

We welcome any comments or suggestion from all people interested in our project and we invite you to read more about it on our website: www.xeric.eu.

